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The Magic Words

Teacher Ina has a trick for today,
She told us some “magic” words we can say.
In glee, we cheered when she raised her hand,
But teacher held a chalk instead of a wand.

She wrote the words up on the board,
“Five magic words we will explore:
‘Thank you’ is the first we’ll learn,
When someone helps or gives a turn.

When someone thanks you otherwise,
Say ‘You’re welcome’ as a reply.
If you make a mistake or make someone cry,
Say ‘I’m sorry’, that’s the way to try.

If you need attention or the crowd gets busy,
Humbly say, ‘Excuse me.’
To ask for something without being impolite,
Always add ‘Please’ every time.

Use these magic words, don’t be shy,
For it will make you courteous and kind.”
The class ends, Teacher Ina waves goodbye,
Now I’ll be a magician no wand required to try.